

Industrial digitalization in the industry 4.0 era: Classification, reuse and authoring of digital models on Digital Twin platforms

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ABSTRACT

Digital Twins (DTs) are real-time digital models that allow for self-diagnosis, self-optimization and self-configuration without the need for human input or intervention. While DTs are a central aspect of the ongoing fourth industrial revolution (I4.0), this leap forward may be reserved for the established, large-cap companies since the adoption of digital technologies among Small and Medium-size Enterprises (SMEs) is still modest. The aim of the H2020 European Project "DIGITbrain" is to support a modular construction of DTs by reusing their fundamental building blocks, i.e., the *Models* that describe the behavior of the DT, their associated *Algorithms* and the *Data* required for the evaluation. By offering these building blocks as a service via a DT Platform (a Digital Twin Environment), the technical barriers among SMEs to adopt these technologies are lowered. This paper describes how digital models can be classified, reused and authored on such DT Platforms. Through experimental analyses of three industrial cases, the paper exemplifies how DTs are employed in relation to product assembly of agricultural robots, polymer injection molding, as well as laser-cutting and sheet-metal forming of aluminum.

1. Introduction

A successful manufacturing company must be agile, innovative, and highly efficient. Not only do companies today face fierce competition from globalization, but product requirements constantly increase due to new legislation, regulations, and customer expectations. Therefore, manufacturing companies already exploit digitalization techniques to be successful in the competitive market. This is the basis of the ongoing fourth industrial revolution (i.e., I4.0), which is already bringing a paradigm shift to manufacturing engineering.

I4.0 builds on the foundation of *Internet of Things* (IoT) technology, where sensors and software are embedded in devices (i.e., cyber-physical systems) to exploit different aspects of computerization. As such, a central aspect of I4.0 is the deployment of the so-called Digital Twins (DTs) [1] that ultimately act as real-time digital models and allow for self-diagnosis, self-optimization and self-configuration without the need for human input or intervention. There is, however, data that indicate that the leap forward offered by I4.0 might be reserved for the established, large-cap companies. For example, the Digital Transformation Scoreboard in EU signals that the adoption of digital technologies among SMEs and mid-caps [2] is below 10%, which

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poses a significant barrier if I4.0 technologies are to be adopted across the entire manufacturing sector.

DTs are becoming increasingly prominent in the manufacturing industry. DTs are capable of optimizing processes and products prior to their execution thanks to their ability of high-fidelity forecasting. In manufacturing industries, DTs can be virtual representations of different systems, e.g., machinery, production lines, products, or any other operation or service related to the manufacturing process. Therefore, DTs can be introduced at any time in the manufacturing process, hence their usefulness is not limited to pre-production planning and design, where prediction and optimization of the product or production lines apply, but they can also be used for maintenance, market analysis, etc. [3].

One way to allow SMEs and mid-caps access to I4.0 technologies is to offer the services via a platform, which is sometimes referred to as a *Digital Twin Environment* [4]. Not only does this lower the investment and infrastructure requirements of companies, but it also gives non-technical staff access to key technologies with only limited training. A Digital Twin Environment can utilize collected data to let models and algorithms remotely steer and optimize products and processes according to the operating conditions. As such, manufacturing companies can now outsource both expertise and parts of the supply chain [5] to service providers, which is referred to as Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) [6–10].

To provide a MaaS platform, several building blocks are needed, many of which have already been explored, among others, in previously funded European H2020 projects. A non-exhaustive list of these EU projects includes: digital services marketplaces for manufacturing companies (CloudiFacturing [11], MANUSQUARE [12]); deployments of smart applications in open-source IoT platforms (FIWARE [12]); cloud orchestration engines (COLA [13,14]); as well as basic research into cyber-physical systems (INTO-CPS [15]) and simulation and forecasting technologies (MAYA [16]). The natural step from present state of the art is to develop a complete set of solutions that further extends the concept of DTs and enable manufacturing companies to tap into the full potential of I4.0. This is the goal of the European H2020 project DIGITbrain and this paper presents the project's novel approach how models for Digital Twins can be made reusable based on the DIGITbrain technology [17].

In order to provide a digital integrated platform, both software and hardware components need to be considered. However, one of the core technologies of the DIGITbrain project is the device-agnostic software-based verification mechanism by the implementation of a lightweight cryptographic library. This paper strictly focuses on Models, as a separate and reusable asset in DIGITbrain.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background for the paper by reviewing related work; Section 3 identifies and reviews a classification of models that may be used on MaaS platforms for evaluation, including the behavior of models, organization, and interaction of coupled models, embedded models, and stateful and stateless models; Section 4 presents the proposed model characterization and metadata structure within DIGITbrain; Section 5 explains how models can be authored; Section 6 lists some of the most relevant results obtained during the first year of DIGITbrain Project leading to enhanced model reusability; and finally, Section 7 concludes the findings of the paper.

2. Background and related work

The use of DTs dates more than 50 years back to the Apollo 13 program, where NASA had designed physical simulators to mirror the conditions that astronauts would experience in the spacecraft during spaceflight [18]. While no formal, generic definition followed its initial introduction, the consensus now characterizes a DT as a digital model with near real-time, bidirectional communication to the physical system [19]. Accordingly, models with one-way communication are

defined as a *digital shadow*, and models without any communication link are no more than digital models of the physical system. A DT can reflect the entire life cycle of a product [20,21], however, targeted domain-specific applications such as monitoring and prediction of crack growth are commonly seen as well [22].

In order to implement and use DTs in an I4.0 manufactory scenario, protocols, access profiles and communications must be set up between hardware and software nodes of the DT architecture [23–25]. Nevertheless, as described in Section 1, the Project DIGITbrain allows a clear separation between different assets, mainly Data, Algorithm and Microservices, and Models. In this scope, only Models are analyzed as an independent and reusable building blocks for DTs in I4.0.

The data to be utilized by the DT (i.e., the cyber-physical system) can be collected from various sensors and other devices, such as cameras, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, gauges (e.g., strain, deformation, temperature), etc. [26]. Naturally, to allow the system to perform any meaningful autonomous decision-making, data must be transmitted in real time or near real time. Recent reviews of data processing in a DT setting can be found in [27,28].

The role of models in a DT setting is to state, estimate and forecast. Models can be purely semantic in the sense that they are solely based on previously collected data. These models are also called database models and can be considered as black-box or gray-box approaches depending on the need for manual configuration. Machine Learning (ML) is the basis for semantic models, and several examples in literature can be found where data has been used to train Neural Networks (NN) [28,29].

Another approach to model system behavior is using physics-based models, also called first-principle models. Here, models are established based on geometrical information, material parameters, process conditions, and the underlying physics is characterized with partial differential equations. In a DT setting, for instance, the governing equations can take the basis in simple considerations of the conservation of energy in thermal system [30] or high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics models [31]. When solving the partial differential equations that govern the physics-based models, discretization methods such as Finite Element Method (FEM) or Finite Volume Method (FVM) must be employed. Therefore, the physical product or process is resolved into a large number of discrete variables, and this system can require significant computational effort to solve. As already discussed, the runtime of simulation models must be close to real-time in a DT setting, so physics-based models are often supplemented with semantic (i.e., ML) [32] or Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) techniques [33,34] to bring down computation time, although the latter technique can be also used to build completely data-driven DTs, as detailed in Section 3.

Based on some prior initiatives in Germany, a joint effort named *Plattform Industrie 4.0* [35] was launched in 2012 to promote the digital transformation of manufacturing, by bringing together companies, their workforces, trade unions, related associations, science, and politics. A comprehensive literature review of I4.0 and related technologies shows that the label *Industry 4.0* was later taken up internationally by many other approaches in the area of *smart manufacturing* [36]. The I4.0 approach was hence at first driven by the German initiative with broad support and high effort in its conceptual foundation, standardization [37] and practical application. The foundation of this approach was mainly based on the results of the working group on Reference Architectures and Standards and Norms, i.e., the *Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0* [38]. Over the years, the platform extended internationally by cooperation or alignment with similar initiatives in other countries in Europe, the US, Japan, and China. An important cornerstone was the alignment with the *Industrial Internet Reference Architecture* (IIRA) of the Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) [39]. As the key concept of I4.0 platform, the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) has been introduced. In alignment with the IIC, the AAS is understood as a realization of DT in terms of I4.0 [40].

While all the previously mentioned research efforts enable the creation of DTs, their construction and creation remain a long and

time-consuming process. Each DT is typically constructed individually, without reusing previous results and existing building blocks. The work described in this paper is the first step to overcome this obstacle by categorizing and describing models with a rich set of metadata to enable their reusability when building DTs.

3. Types of models

The DIGITbrain Project includes and supports several kinds of models. A model in DIGITbrain is an asset that contains the knowledge related to a specific industrial product instance (i.e., a concrete manufacturing machine or production line), which can hence describe and forecast the behavior of such an instance when specific operating conditions are given (n.b., the process of forecasting a system's behavior according to specific operating conditions is also known as model evaluation). In this section, we detail the different model types.

3.1. Co-simulation models

Models related to Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) are often difficult to develop, due to the large variety of sub-systems (e.g., networks, control algorithms, mechanical components, electrical circuits, sensors) and components with different formalisms. Since sub-systems and components can be reused in different scenarios and applications, it becomes very helpful to be able to model them separately, instead of creating a single monolithic model that includes all of them. For this purpose, co-simulation is a very useful approach for coupling together the different parts of a whole system.

The sub-systems and components are created by model developers and exported as co-simulation units [41]. In order to perform co-simulation of a complete system, these co-simulation units need a standard way of interacting with each other. Since manufacturing systems are typically produced by a combination of heterogeneous components, these components are usually supplied by several legal entities; hence protection of the intellectual property for the underlying model is needed.

The Functional Mockup Interface (FMI) [42] is a widely used solution for the above described problem where the orchestration of combining differing simulation units is made by independent orchestration engines [43]. FMI is a cross-platform and open-source standard to exchange models and perform co-simulation. Components that conform to the FMI standard are called Functional Mockup Units (FMUs). An FMU is distributed as an archive with the file extension *.fmu*. An FMU contains the following:

- an XML-file with metadata, definitions of all the variables inside the FMU, and desired outputs
- implementation in source and/or binary form, specifically:
 - binaries: this directory contains the executable files of the FMU and can also contain shared library executable code for different OS (Operating System) platforms
 - resources (optional): the contents of this directory can be used by the FMU during execution time
 - sources (optional): the source code of the FMU, compiled to produce the shared libraries placed in the binaries directory
- additional Data, such as documentation

It is important to remark that the model itself inside the FMU may be distributed as binary and hence can be exchanged as *black boxes*, which is also beneficial to protect the intellectual property of the source code.

3.2. Machine learning models

The use of ML in industrial manufacturing offers immense potential for the optimization of procedures and processes. As a result of their effectiveness, they are used in various tasks like computer vision, speech and pattern recognition, natural language processing etc. [44]. However, the creation of the required models requires expert knowledge, since modern production plants are very individual and thus also very complex. The goal of the methods is to capture interrelationships that cannot be comprehensively achieved by classical modeling with the aim of capturing the optimization potential, such as product quality, resource utilization and to be able to initiate corresponding improvements in the sense of predictive maintenance, containment of unplanned machine failures or an improved quality assurance process. To develop models in these application domains, significant amounts of data are needed in the first stage of preparation. These data need to be collected and prepared with the help of experts, matching the applied ML technical requirements and the production-automation technologies. They serve as *training data* for the model.

ML models are usually trained in a High Performance Computing Cluster (HPC) and subsequently deployed in less compute-intensive environments, such as highly available computers in the cloud or edge devices. The *trained model* can be used for prediction, feature extraction, decision support, and pattern recognition once adaptation to the training data is complete. Such a trained model consists of a collection of numbers (*called weights*), rules, and data structures specific to ML algorithms, required for decision-making and prediction. For example, in an ML deep learning application on an image classification use case, the NN algorithm, together with the backpropagation [45] and gradient descent algorithms [46], generates an ML model and optimizes the training data, which consists of a collection of correctly classified images.

3.3. Reduced Order Models

Together with ML, ROM is another popular technique among AI methods for DTs. It shows several similarities with ML, as detailed below.

ROM models are created through a numerical strategy that aims to transform a complex, time- and resources-consuming simulation or laboratory test-based model into a significantly simpler system. ROM models can be obtained through both intrusive [47–50] or non-intrusive methods [51–54]. Intrusive methods allow to directly modify the system's equations and are especially useful when the system's equations are known, but too complex to be solved for a general case, in a reasonable amount of time and with limited resources. On the other hand, non-intrusive methods can be employed either when the system's equations are known or completely unknown. These methods are hence purely data-based and can be compared to ML data-trained model.

An example for generating non-intrusive ROM models is provided by CAELIA™ Twinkle authoring tool [55], i.e., a library for creating Tensor-Rank-Decomposition (TRD)-based ROMs, according to Eq. (1). Twinkle allows for an extensive manifold exploration, and it can work on dense, sparse or even unstructured data; for further details please refer to Zambrano et al. [56]. According to Eq. (1), the TRD method is a powerful method for simplifying and understanding a system. In fact, through the TRD approach it is possible to describe the system's behavior (i.e., output) by means of independent functions, one for each system variable separately. Using the TRD method, a problem with N variables can therefore be expressed as the product of N one-dimensional functions (i.e., one for each system variable).

$$F(v_1, \dots, v_N) = \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \prod_{n=1}^N f_{m,n}(v_n) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Example of a SoS characterization from an LCA perspective.

where M is the ROM's approximation order, so that the first addend corresponds to a first approximation of the system, while following terms are corrections to it, being α_m , $m = 1, \dots, M$ weighting coefficients with generally decreasing values.

CAELIA™ ROMs, for instance, can be easily obtained from input data files such as .txt or .csv that typically include data points where both inputs and output values are provided, similarly to supervised ML algorithms [57]. These ROM models can be easily embedded and managed by virtually any kind of environment, e.g., desktop applications or web interfaces, where users can provide keyboard inputs and navigate to obtain real-time results. The computed ROM model file can be straightforwardly embedded in different platforms as a .txt file that includes all the necessary information and parameters to compute the system's response in real-time.

3.4. System of Systems models

System of Systems (SoS) models can be based on both structural and behavioral models. One example of a SoS model, from a structural point of view, is the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tool [58] model applied in a manufacturing domain. LCA is a well-acknowledged methodology for analyzing the environmental impacts of manufacturing processes along their entire life cycle. LCA assessment leverages on the use of well-founded background data that enable users to personalize their operation information so to calculate the environmental indicators that represent impacts related to a specific process. This process is supported by the LCA Process Templates (PT) tool which creates process characterization by formalizing the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) description, where for each specific process inputs and outputs are identified and quantified. LCI considers resources (i.e., inputs) coming from the ecosphere (e.g., raw material, water) or from another technosphere (e.g., ancillary material such as lubricating oil) and energy of various types. LCI assesses emissions (i.e., outputs), such as waste, products and co-products. LCI data represent the variables belonging to the LCA model and are retrieved directly from the production line or collected manually through IoT devices. Fig. 1 shows an example of LCA process characterization. The figure shows how LCI output of a certain process can become the input for another process in a SoS model.

From a LCA point of view, an output of a specific process (i.e., a system) can be formalized as an input to another process. Since a process is considered the fundamental unit for the LCA evaluation, a complex system might be represented by a production machine (as

supplier of several processes) or a production line (obtained as the composition of production machines or single processes). This approach can be repeated by composing more processes on various levels of complexity.

In addition to LCI data, LCA methodology is also based on Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) information on the impacts related to the inventory, i.e., the computed environmental indicators. LCIA data, for the analysis of a specific system, can be calculated from the LCI data via characterization factors, i.e., factors meant to translate the inventory into environmental impacts. On the basis of the approach explained before, the LCA assessment of a SoS can be obtained as a composition of LCA assessments of each system.

Another type of SoS models supported by DIGITbrain is integrated 3D and Discrete Event Simulation (DES) models. DES models are behavioral model which describe the evolution of a system during a given time, in which the simulated time is advanced at discrete intervals only when a change in the system occurs, updating the state of the system. In DIGITbrain, DES is supported through the DDSimulator simulation engine, a DES tool with integrated 3D virtual environment. Simulation models are composed by reusable elements called prototypes, each one representing a component of the simulated system (machine, transporters, logic module); prototype instances communicate among each other with ports that are used to exchange data between different modules. The models realized can be used to simulate the system for a period of time and obtain statistics that give information on the performance of the system in the simulated conditions. A graphical Integrated Development Environment (IDE) called DDD Model Editor supports the visual editing of both prototypes and models.

3.5. Stateful vs. stateless models

Some models always generate the same results for a specific set of in-slot values when instantiated (i.e., stateless models), while other models depend on their previous state and must therefore remain persistently instantiated (i.e., stateful models). On the one hand, in stateless models, outputs only depend on the model itself and current inputs, such as static equilibrium simulations, non-recurrent NNs, and LCAs. On the other hand, for stateful models, the outputs also depend on their internal state and thereby on a potentially unbounded number of previous inputs. Examples include transient or dynamic simulations and recurrent NNs.

Distinguishing between stateful and stateless models is particularly important for the correct evaluation of models. On the one hand, while stateless models can be reconstructed at any time, stateful models and their evaluating algorithms must remain instantiated on a given compute node. Alternatively, the algorithm must support serializing its state and restoring it on a different machine. On the other hand, keeping stateless models instantiated is not a requirement, although it might be beneficial to avoid instantiation overhead. In this context, it is important to consider the cost of on-demand instantiation of a model with a given algorithm, as well as (de)serialization costs for stateful models. If the cost of on-demand instantiation is less than the benefit derived from continuous model evaluation, then on-demand instantiation might be a better choice.

4. Reusable models for DIGITbrain

4.1. Reuse in the DIGITbrain ecosystem

The key to efficiently create DTs lies in the reuse of existing artifacts. The reuse of software artifacts is a well-established concept in software engineering [59]. The DIGITbrain ecosystem enables reuse by decomposing DTs into their constituting parts, i.e., data, models, and algorithms. Metadata describing these assets and their physical locations in external repositories are stored in the Platform, enabling users to create DTs by composing the parts into a Data-Model-Algorithm (DMA) tuple.

Focusing on models, the core problem is not the availability, but the identification, occasional adaptation, and composition of models with suitable data and algorithms to create DTs (i.e., DMA Tuples). In DIGITbrain a model classification has been developed to allow a model developer creating a meta-description, which ensures discoverability and composability of models with algorithms by DT experts after publication.

The major challenge tackled by DIGITbrain is to present the characterization in such a way that the model user can conveniently find the right model for efficient reuse. The core service responsible for enabling reuse is the DIGITbrain Asset Metadata Registry that stores a rich set of metadata about all DIGITbrain assets, including models. The actual models are only referenced from this Registry and stored in external model repositories (the project set up a sample model repository for demonstration purposes). The access service relies on the metadata descriptions to provide filtering, search functionality and to assure that the selected model is fed into the chosen algorithm at execution time.

Within this context, the main classification characteristics proposed in DIGITbrain are the various aspects of the model, for example modeling language, model inputs and outputs, and the structure and construction of the model. Moreover, further characteristics are taken into account, related to the evaluation of the model by the selected algorithm, such as its storage requirements during execution, and the information about the model's fidelity in its range of validity.

For this purpose, generalized metadata description tables were created (see Tables 1 to 3), to be filled with the selected characteristics of each model. The tables, represented as key-value pairs, are described in the following sections.

4.2. Model metadata description

The process of publishing a model on the DIGITbrain Platform requires providing all information needed for the model to be evaluated with a compatible algorithm. Once the model information has been collected, it can be published on the DIGITbrain Platform, using the dedicated DIGITbrain publishing interface.

As mentioned earlier, in order to facilitate data collection from different types of models, metadata specifications for models have been defined as a common structure to be used within the DIGITbrain Platform and are stored as key-value pairs in a relational database. Model

Table 1
Selection of model metadata related to model definition.

Key	Type	Description
ID	UUID	SemVer ID of the model.
name	string	Name of the model.
version	SemVer2	Model version.
license	string	Licensing model chosen from a fixed set of known licenses.
provider	enum	Provider name: Institution or Person.
provider_contacts	obj	(optional) Dictionary with keys being phone, email, address.
AuthTool	obj	Authoring tool used to create the model.
type	enum	Model type, e.g., ML, LCA, 3D FEM, CFD, system simulation, discrete event simulation, or co-simulation; any algorithm that supports the given type can be used to evaluate this model.
fidelity	number	(optional) Error of the model's prediction.
model_URI	URI	Where the model(s) file(s) is/are stored.
state_depend	bool	Defines whether a model is stateful or stateless, c.f. Section 3.

metadata were designed not simply based on the analysis of various models, but also taking the characteristics of algorithms evaluating these models, and the requirements for the deployment and execution of the resulting DMA Tuples (DTs) into consideration. Model metadata are divided into three main categories: definition, parametrization, and publication. Tables 1 to 3 show a selection of model metadata related to each category, while Tables 4 to 6 are optional metadata tables very specifically referring to co-simulation models. A full specification will be released on the DIGITbrain Website (<https://digitbrain.eu>) in the near future.

Model definition fields (Table 1) include a human-readable description of models, model properties (i.e., I/O, hardware requirements etc.), and references to the externally stored models. This section contains an ID value, which is generated automatically by the DIGITbrain Asset Publishing Interface. The other fields are provided by the asset owner through the publishing interface. These include generic information as the model's name, version, license, and provider fields. The *AuthTool* key provides information about the authoring tool used for creating the model, while further fields describe its type (e.g., ML, LCA, etc.), the model's fidelity (i.e., reliability of prediction or errors), a URI for storage location and a *state_depend* key that differentiates between stateful and stateless models (see Section 3).

The parametrization section takes into account I/O and other parameters that might be needed for its evaluation. In Table 2 the generic features to be considered for model parametrization are listed, such as the *in_slots* (i.e., inputs and parameters) and *outputs* fields. These are composed of a unique model's key, a name, the number of dimensions, model's units (i.e., human-readable name, SI – International System of Units – exponents in a [m, s, mol, A, K, cd, kg] format, a scale offset if needed and a scale's order of magnitude), a default value if available, valid range, and a description. Moreover, the model parametrization metadata foresees optional fields presented in Tables 4 to 6 and related to co-simulation, in which dependencies, OS and hardware requirements are covered.

Publication metadata (Table 3) is currently a simple human-readable description of the model. However, this can potentially be replaced with a more complex ontological approach in the future that enables the automated interpretation and selection of models (a functionality that is not currently supported by the DIGITbrain Platform and done by the human operators/users).

Using the metadata specified above, model reusability becomes a reality. Once *Models* are published separately from other DIGITbrain *Assets* (e.g., *Algorithms* and *Data*), dynamic composition of these assets

Table 2
Selection of model metadata related to model parametrization.

Key	Type	Description
<code>in_slots</code>	<code>array[object]</code>	Input values and/or parameters for the model. The objects in this array contain input's or parameter's: unique key, name, number of dimensions, units (i.e., a human-readable name, SI – International System of Units – exponents in a [m, s, mol, A, K, cd, kg] format, a scale offset if needed and a scale's order of magnitude), default value if available, ranges (i.e., minima and maxima) and a description
<code>outputs</code>	<code>array[object]</code>	Model-specific outputs. Structured analogously to <code>in_slots</code> .
<code>cosim_solver_info</code>	object (<i>optional</i>)	Co-simulation models bundle binary solvers. Therefore, execution information such as operating system, CPU and GPU architecture, etc. are required in that case (see Tables 4 to 6).

Table 3
Selection of model metadata related to model publication.

Key	Type	Description
<code>description</code>	CommonMark	Human-readable description of the model, e.g., version, scope (simulation, control, etc.). Provided as CommonMark Markdown for rendering as a web page.

Table 4
Cosim_solver_info Dependant FMUs metadata (*optional*).

Key	Type	Description
<code>dependencies</code>	<code>array[URI]</code>	Dependant FMUs for co-simulation.

Table 5
Cosim_solver_info OS requirements metadata (*optional*).

Key	Type	Description
<code>osArch</code>	enum	OS architecture type (e.g., x86_64).
<code>osType</code>	enum	OS type (e.g., Windows, Linux).
<code>osDistribution</code>	enum	OS distribution (e.g., Ubuntu, Fedora).
<code>osVersion</code>	SemVer2	Version of the OS.

into executable DMA Tuples becomes possible at run-time. Obviously, the compatibility of the combined assets still needs to be checked and assured, either by the human composer (as in the current version of the DIGITbrain Platform) or via an ontology-based automated approach (which may be considered for the future). However, from the published metadata the DIGITbrain Platform is capable of generating the executable “artifact” automatically by combining the model with the algorithm that evaluates it and the data that is required as input for the calculation, without further human intervention.

Please note that while the above-mentioned composition and automatic code generation are important and interesting topics, these are out of the scope of this paper as we only concentrate on models and their reusability.

5. Authoring of DIGITbrain models

There are several authoring tools for generating, importing, managing, evaluating, and exporting various models. In this section the authoring tools related to DIGITbrain models detailed in Section 3 are described. Please note that such authoring tools are outside the DIGITbrain Platform. With such decision DIGITbrain does not limit the choice of authoring tools that can be used to generate models. Any authoring tool can be applied, and the generated models can be registered in a uniform way with the Platform, as described in Section 4. As a consequence, the authoring tools detailed in this section are examples only. Other authoring tools can also be used freely in relation to the DIGITbrain approach.

5.1. Authoring tools for co-simulation models

Many modeling and simulation tools are used to author functional mockup unit (FMUs) – co-simulation units – conforming to the functional mockup interface (FMI) standard; over 100 of these authoring

tools can be found on the FMI website [60]. Using FMI, FMUs can be authored by the manufacturers of industrial products and shared among the users.

The Integrated Tool Chain for Model-based Design of Cyber-Physical Systems (INTO-CPS toolchain), a Project led by Aarhus University, is an example co-simulation toolchain [15,61]. The INTO-CPS toolchain consists of a framework (i.e., a family of tools) built around FMI-compatible co-simulation for a collaborative development of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS). The core of the INTO-CPS toolchain is the co-simulation orchestration engine called Maestro [43]. This essentially enables any authoring tool that can export their models to an FMU to be usable. The toolchain integrates with FMU authoring tools such as Modelio, and Overture [62,63]. Modelio is an open-source modeling environment capable of generating FMUs from SysML profiles [64]. Overture is a tool used to specify and execute formal models described in Vienna Development Method (VDM) [65]. Overture is capable of exporting VDM models into FMUs. Other FMU authoring tools do exist; OpenModelica is one such example as an interactive development environment for system representation in Modelica language [66,67]. The three tools mentioned above model Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) in different ways and export these into FMUs. The users can then apply the INTO-CPS toolchain to import these FMUs and combine multiple FMUs into a co-simulation model of an industrial product.

5.2. Authoring tools for machine learning models

As ML models are generated through the data driven training process on ML algorithms, necessary algorithm packages have to be developed in the particular ML framework. These pre-configured algorithms are created with the help of external authoring tools. Such authoring tools create specific microservices performing certain data handling tasks and build up an ML algorithm by combining one or more individual microservices. In ML applications DIGITbrain makes use of reference architectures, combination of widely-used machine learning tools and libraries that can be deployed by *one click* in the cloud, to enable this automated creation of containerized, ready-to-use software stacks, for non-experienced users. Many steps of the authoring process could be automated, by providing domain specific templates and building on tools that are already available, for example Jupyter Labs [68].

Within the reference architectures, the domain experts (data scientists) can build on and use well-known ML frameworks. The DIGITbrain Platform provides a fast way to reuse models and train them individually with customized datasets. This fast and easy reproducibility of implementations provides a very fast way to implement AI in production. This model processing takes place in a predefined working environment supported by ML frameworks such as TensorFlow [69], PyTorch [70], etc. After training, the generated models can be stored in ML framework-specific formats and executed on less powerful hardware. To support model portability, the open source community has proposed the Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) standard [71]. With this approach, we propose a standard to exchange and transfer trained ML models to the different devices for applications. As another option, we also rely on the *SavedModel* format [72] favored by Google.

Table 6
Cosim_solver_info Hardware requirements metadata (optional).

Key	Type	Description
recommendedNumberOfGPUCores	number	Recommended number of GPU cores.
minimumNumberOfGPUCores	number	Minimum required number of GPU cores.
recommendedGPURAM	number	Recommended GPU memory.
minimumGPURAM	number	Minimum required GPU memory.
recommendedRAM	number	Recommended Memory.
minimumRAM	number	Minimum required memory.
recommendedCPUs	number	Recommended number of CPU cores.
minimumCPUs	number	Minimum required number of CPU cores.
requiredDiskSpace	number	Required amount of disk space in GB.

5.3. Authoring tools for Reduced Order Models

As described in Section 3, ROM is an umbrella of methods that can be helpful in different situations where a reduction in terms of system variables and their relations should be taken into consideration. The most common scenarios for ROM application are the followings:

- a large amount of data is to be analyzed,
- the physics behind the system under investigation remains uncertain,
- the system's equations are well known, but the solution is not trivial and/or its computation is highly time- and resource consuming.

To support such scenarios, the CAELIA™ tool was developed at ITAINNOVA for ROM generation and management, using TRD technique. CAELIA™ can be used for different manufacturing processes, such as injection molding, rubber extrusion, hot stamping, and laser welding. CAELIA™ consists of a set of libraries, where models are generated using Twinkle library [56]. Since TRD-based ROM models are based on data (please, refer to Section 3) that can be obtained through experiments, simulations or by mathematically solving equations (if known), a careful Design of Experiment (DoE) must be performed beforehand. Hence, this authoring tool also includes a library for automatic DoE with an enhanced space coverage. Additionally, CAELIA™ includes different optimization algorithms and several visualization interfaces. All these libraries and tools can be combined and used for enhancing ROM computation and management.

CAELIA™'s ROMs are a valuable tool, not only capable of forecasting unexplored behaviors of the system, but also useful for optimization, i.e., for finding the system's operating conditions that correspond to a desired output.

The CAELIA™ toolset has been already tested against a large variety of cases, such as fluid- and thermodynamics, friction modeling, etc. In Section 6 an injection application CAELIA™ will be detailed.

5.4. Authoring tools for System of Systems models

The Sustainability Assessment Application (SAA) is an evolution of an already existing application developed by SUPSI, i.e., Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana, in previous EU projects (MANUTELLIGENCE [73] and MANUSQUARE [12]). SAA is an authoring tool which allows users to characterize the processes provided by a production machine or a production line according to a LCA point of view. Fig. 2 shows an example of formalization of a set of processes. The tool enables the users to specify the SoS composition where the output flow (LCI output) of a certain process can be formalized as input flow (LCI input) for another process. The model underlying the SAA has been extensively described in Section 3, where the concept of PT emerges as an element related to a specific Functional Unit (i.e., the quantification of the system's function analyzed by LCA), that is meant to quantify the function of the process under investigation (examples are: 1 h of milling process execution or 1 kg of removed steel for milling, 1 kg of injected plastic for injection molding, etc.; please refer to Fig. 2). Starting from the background data, retrieved from a LCIA

database such as Ecoinvent [74], the percentage contribution of inputs and outputs to the selected environmental indicators are evaluated in order to identify process parameters critical from the LCA point of view. For instance, concerning the Climate Change indicator of the injection molding operation, it has been estimated that inputs such as *Electricity* and *Natural Gas (heat)* represent over 80% of the indicator value's input. Through this sort of Pareto analysis, performed by LCA experts and partially automatized by the SSA, whenever a new operation type is introduced into the ecosystem, the LCI data affecting most of the process in terms of environmental impacts is determined. The identified crucial parameters are hence considered as *free* ones that, starting from the default value proposed by the SSA, can be customized by the supplier, together with more specific indicators values, in order to better represent its manufacturing operation. The Pareto analysis, here presented only for the Climate Change impact category, has to be performed on the complete set of the selected indicators. By clicking on a specific process, it is possible to visualize the LCI data characterizing the whole, where the most relevant ones from the impact point of view are highlighted in green, as shown in Fig. 3. Only the highlighted LCI can be customized by the user considering a different input value (n.b., the user usually knows the amount of the electricity that is actually consumed by a given machine).

Another example for SoS authoring tools is the DDDSimulator which a DES tool with an integrated 3D virtual environment. Simulation models are composed by reusable elements called prototypes each one representing a component of the simulated system (machine, transporters, logic module). Prototype instances communicate among each other with ports that are used to exchange data between different modules. The developed models can be used to simulate the behavior of the entire system by obtaining statistics that give information on the performance of the system within the simulated conditions. A graphical IDE called DDD Model Editor supports the visual editing of both prototypes and models. The modules can be combined in different configurations to realize DTs of plants to evaluate and compare the performances of alternative design. Due to this modular approach, with each module encapsulating the behavior of a complex system, the modules can be reused to compose SoS models.

6. Experimental results

In this section the results obtained in some of the experiments performed during the first year of the DIGITbrain Project are summarized. The examples described in this section show how DIGITbrain architecture helps developing DTs. Moreover, the experimental results obtained during the first year of the project, some of them being summarized below, show that the DIGITbrain's framework can be straightforwardly applied in I4.0 to accelerate industrial digitalization.

6.1. Co-simulation in agricultural robots

AgroIntelli manufactures and sells semi-autonomous agricultural vehicles to farmers, called Robotti. Robottis are delivered to farmers and used in diverse agricultural environments. The company expects a rapid growth in the sales of Robotti and would like to know the best

Process list:

Name	Group	Process	Geography	Reference Product	Quantity	
My Injection	New Group	injection moulding	RER	injection moulding	1	kg
My Alu milling	New Group	aluminium milling, small parts	RoW	aluminium removed by milling, small parts	1	kg
My Alu Turning	New Group	aluminium turning, average, conventional	RoW	aluminium removed by turning, average, conventional	1	kg

ADD PROCESS

Rows per page: 5 1-3 of 3

Fig. 2. List of the processes, for example belonging to a production line.

Characterize: injection moulding

INPUT OUTPUT

Input flows:

Name	Geography	Type	Unit quantity	Impacts Contribute
electricity, medium voltage	Europe(RER)	FROM_TECHNOSPHERE	1,48 kWh	69.23%
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	Europe(RER)	FROM_TECHNOSPHERE	4,21 MJ	13.13%
solvent, organic	Global(GLO)	FROM_TECHNOSPHERE	0,0447 kg	6.90%
chemical, organic	Global(GLO)	FROM_TECHNOSPHERE	0,0128 kg	2.89%
EUR-flat pallet	Europe(RER)	FROM_TECHNOSPHERE	0,00146 unit	1.48%

ADD

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 18

Input elementary flows:

Name	Type	Unit quantity	Impacts Contribute
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin	FROM_ENVIRONMENT	0,011 m3	.

ADD

Rows per page: 5 1-1 of 1

Fig. 3. Example of process characterization (LCI input and output) by the SSA. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

way of scaling up the production based on the expected sales. Right now, AgroIntelli assembles each robot on a made-to-order basis, at a single workstation, with predominantly manual work being required to assemble and interconnect all subcomponents and devices to each order. AgroIntelli would like to design and validate an automated manufacturing line for Robotti that can take the manufacturing blueprint and produce the robot.

Additionally, certain parts of Robotti, for example the air filter, the hydraulic oil, or the oil filter, need to be replaced during scheduled maintenance at different service intervals. When required, farmers also place orders for Robotti parts. Once the part orders from farmers are received, AgroIntelli needs to integrate the production of these parts into the manufacturing schedule. The updated production schedule will have to produce an expected delivery date for all the ordered parts.

A DT of AgroIntelli's manufacturing line helps the company performing an analysis of alternative scenarios for future factory construction. The projected manufacturing capacity, based on estimated sales and the manufacturing requirements of various parts based on sample Robotti usage scenarios, are key inputs of the factory DT. On the other hand, a feasible production schedule is the key output of the DT. The creation of the DT for the manufacturing line is done using the FMI [60] co-simulation standard. The key elements/workstations of the manufacturing line are modeled as FMUs. The DT for the manufacturing line is created by putting the FMUs together as one system and then co-simulated using Maestro [43]. The co-simulation *Algorithm* uses a configuration file for connecting the FMUs and performing a single co-simulation.

The factory DT is created from reusable FMUs which together form the *Model* of the DT. The Maestro co-simulation *Algorithm* becomes the *Algorithm* evaluating the factory DT *Model*. The evaluation of the factory *Model* by the Maestro *Algorithm* also requires *Data*. This *Data* come from the planned production schedules and the on-demand part orders from farmers.

In the context of agile manufacturing practices, it is important to keep the manufacturing line flexible and reroute the parts based on the

current demand. Therefore, FMUs need to be connected differently for co-simulating alternative manufacturing scenarios. One such scenario could be the creation of multiple models of Robotti. Another scenario could be the installation of parallel workstations to scale up the production of complicated machine parts. Each of these alternative scenarios can be explored by using one factory *Model* (implemented as multiple FMUs) and different co-simulation configurations. Therefore, the Maestro co-simulation *Algorithm* is reusable for all co-simulation models. Additionally, different manufacturers can bring in their co-simulation models and perform co-simulation using Maestro co-simulation *Algorithm*. The factory *Model* can also be reused by AgroIntelli to perform different design scenarios for the planned manufacturing line. In other words, the same *Model* can be used to perform Design Space Exploration (DSE) for designing an optimum manufacturing line [15]. Since each FMU represents a factory workstation, there is a potential for reusing single FMUs to create new co-simulation scenarios of other factory configurations/factories. As a result, a DT created for AgroIntelli is reusable within the broader manufacturing industry too. This has been made possible by the clean separation of *Data*, *Algorithm*, and *Model* of the factory DT using the DIGITbrain approach.

6.2. Reduced order models for injection molding

A physically based DT for a thermoplastic injection molding consists of the digitalization of a thermoplastic material injection molding process for the quick initial set-up of process parameters and the optimization during production. The DT is based on the offline exploitation of state-of-the-art numerical simulation tools to model the relevant fluid-dynamics, heat transfer and thermo-mechanical physical mechanisms, as well as subsequent encapsulation of relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) into ROMs that are made available for the user to get a real time virtual try-out and estimated production quality monitoring.

Within the DIGITbrain experiment performed for Inymon, a Spanish injection molding company, current state-of-the-art simulation models

representing the physics of the material transformation process, including transient flow fluid-dynamics, heat transfer by conduction and convection, and solid thermo-mechanics were used. Specific material relations, such as non-Newtonian rheology and equations of state, reproduce the material's behavior. These models are expressed as a set of differential equations corresponding to the conservative laws (i.e., mass, moment, energy) in fluid and solid domains. These physical equations are solved using Volume of Fluid (VoF)/FEM by the Moldex3D commercial program [75]. Furthermore, an offline execution of a simulation DoE is carried out to allow the virtual exploration of the *Model* to generate a database of simulation results, covering suitable variation ranges of the processing parameters (i.e., melt temperature, filling time/ram speed, switch over point, packing pressure and time, coolant temperature and flow rate, cooling time, etc.).

As mentioned previously, online process modeling for quality control requires real-time simulation capabilities, which cannot be achieved by executing the computationally intensive physically based simulation models (as these require hours to run) within a real cycle time (i.e., <1 min). Creating ROMs has proved to be a valid approach to provide real-time responses to Physically Based Simulations (PBS). A ROM retains only the relevant information required for quality evaluation (i.e., selected KPIs) and process control. Among the different techniques available for ROM generation, *a posteriori* or non-intrusive techniques have a higher potential, especially combined with real *Data*. CAELIA™'s ROM generation, based on the factorization of the information through TRD approach, results into a sequence of products of separable 1D functions that can be solved *on the fly* (see Eq. (1)), allowing having a transfer function directly related to input parameters, independently [56].

Within the scope of the DIGITbrain Project, the ROM generation solution, used to build the ROMs, has been deployed in the cloud-based platform as a job. Moreover, the CAELIA™ App including a Graphical User Interface (GUI) has also been deployed on a Virtual Machine (VM) instance on the Platform. The GUI allows the user to compose tuples of ROMs (as DIGITbrain *Models*), input *Data*, as well as evaluation and optimization *Algorithms* to try finding the parameters describing the best injection molding process.

ROMs are specific of each injection process (IP instance), as they are built on physically based simulation *Data* generated for a specific physical instance, which makes the reusability of ROMs anything but straightforward. Nevertheless, the algorithms used to build ROMs and the CAELIA™ App are generic, so that different users can employ them and upload their ROMs and *Data* from other injection molding lines. A possible way to reuse ROMs would be the development of an expert system that, by analyzing a database of ROMs, generated for different injection molding processes, could extract rules of dependencies for typical results obtained from defined process conditions (knowledge-based reasoning). As a further step, the aforementioned expert system could also, based on the characteristics of the part to be injected, be able to create a new ROM backbone by proposing 1D functions for the TRD factorization, that represent the dependency of a result on a specific process condition. This *Model* could be used as a low fidelity *Model* to analyze tendencies or as the basis for a new adjustment, based on PBS or measured *Data*.

6.3. System of systems models for laser-cutting and forming of aluminum

Creation of a simulation tool which allows the end user to create alternative layouts of production lines for forming aluminum sheets and compare the performances of the different solutions has high importance. The main limitations that reflect the current status of most EU manufacturing SMEs in the utilization of DTs of production lines, are the following:

- the inability to perform real-time *what-if* analysis based on the actual plant *Data*, that strongly impairs the ability to promptly tackle production needs and constraints,

- the inability to use DT in the bidding/negotiation phase, that hampers the possibility to demonstrate all plant configurations, leading to under-exploited machine customization potential,
- the inability to provide simulation services and analytics empowered by the knowledge developed all along the plant's life-cycle reduces plant productivity and efficiency, reducing customer satisfaction,
- the dichotomy existing between the real plant and its digital representation makes simulation and analysis tools of little use after the ramp-up phase, leading to under-exploited productivity during machine usage due to the inability to use context-synchronized and history-aware simulation.

The inability to connect to existing manufacturing plants in many cases comes from the presence of legacy control hardware, as this legacy hardware does not have the ability to be connected to the external world. Investing in updating the control hardware of a manufacturing line usually requires high investment. To overcome this, *CPSisers* are deployed at shop-floor level. Such *CPSisers* are software and hardware components used to turn the machines into CPS. The task of developing the *CPSiser* was assigned to NXT control, an automation consulting company partner of the DIGITbrain Project. To interact with the real plant, NXT control developed a *CPSiser*, which allows legacy hardware of different brands and vendors to be interfaced with the FIWARE [12] communication infrastructure, sending *Data* from sensor and Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) to the DT to synchronize it with the reality. Simulation prototypes for eight modules were created, which allowed the simulation of two alternative layouts with different configurations of the unloading system and selecting the better performer. The simulation *Model* was then uploaded on a VM in the cloud and from there it can be accessed and executed via an internet browser loading different production plans.

Within this context, the discrete simulation engine (DDDSimulator) [76] was used for SoS analysis. The DDSimulator is a simulation tool for integrated 3D and DES, developed and distributed by Technol-ogy Transfer System (TTS). This simulator enables its users to design new layouts combining reusable modules, each representing an element of the plant such as machines, transporters, feeding systems and robots. The simulation models can be used to assess the performance of alternative layouts, after which the *Model* of the effective plant can be uploaded to the DIGITbrain Platform and used to simulate the performances of different production plans.

To simulate a production line, the end user uses the Domain-Driven Design (DDD) *Model* editor, a standalone Windows application that can be installed on a Windows PC. The user drags modules from the prototype catalog into the 3D environment. Each prototype simulates the behavior of a component of the plant and several instances of the same prototype can be added to one simulation *Model*. Once an instance is dragged into the 3D environment, it can be moved and rotated to adjust its position in space. Each specific instance also has parameters that can be configured, representing the peculiarities of the specific instance and enabling the configuration of both logical or physical characteristics of the module. For example, the speed of a linear axis in a robot or the length of a conveyor are parameters that can be configured for a module. Modules can exchange information between them using ports, and ports are connected in the visual interface to allow all the modules to work based on the entire logic of the system. This modular structure allows for the re-usability of modules, which already encapsulate the behavioral model of a single complex system, to compose SoS models of several complex production systems combining the reusable elements.

7. Conclusion

The European H2020 Project "DIGITbrain" aims at creating an integrated digital platform that enables Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) which lowers the barriers for Small and Medium-size Enterprises (SMEs) to adopt key Industry 4.0 technologies. The demands for

increased production and the high standards of consumers' expectations in the Industry 4.0 (I4.0) era encourage the introduction of Digital Twins (DTs) in the manufacturing industry, especially to help SMEs forecasting and optimizing their systems (e.g., processes, machinery, production lines) under different operating conditions. Offering MaaS on an integrated digital platform is an efficient way to achieve that.

In the paper, it was highlighted how DIGITbrain's overall concept supports the reusability of *Models* by separating the fundamental building blocks of DTs, including the *Model* itself, its *Algorithms* and *Data*, with a rich set of metadata. Moreover, given the definition of a DT as a virtual model of a physical system, models represent a crucial asset for industrial digitalization and the introduction of DTs in manufacturing processes. We further detailed some model types that are currently supported by the DIGITbrain Platform, such as co-simulation, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and System of Systems (SoS) models. Moreover, we detailed three representative case studies, where practical applications of DTs were delivered to manufacturing SMEs and their end-users.

Further work is being conducted towards the generation of improved models for several applications. The models will be published on the project's integrated platform which is currently being upgraded to grant scalability, parallelization and efficiency.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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